

Simulating Plankton - getting it right in the era of Digital Twins of The Ocean

Data to support plankton model construction

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Author Contributions

Flynn designed the project and task. Others, notably Sherr, helped to improve the task description and the template. All contributed to depositing information to the database. Flynn undertook the initial analysis of the Results and drafted the Discussion. All contributed to finalising the report.

Executive Summary

This work describes the outcomes from a subcomponent of a project funded by the NERC (UK) during 2023, with the overarching aim of facilitating the construction of the next generation of plankton simulation models by engaging with experts in real plankton physiology and ecology. Over 30 experts, covering plankton from viruses to krill, contributed to various facets of the project. They were selected specifically for their empirical interests; modellers per se were not included. This component had 13 contributors.

This work includes information to assist contributors in identifying data of use to modellers, including considerations of the types of data that modellers need, and the challenges inherent in certain data types.

Contributors were requested to provide exemplar references that they considered supportive of plankton modelling targeted at developing digital twins. These data were deposited in a database held in an Excel spreadsheet file (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948648>). The database, containing over 120 entries, can be explored using multi-level sort functions. Although entries contain data dominated by primary producers, temperature, light and inorganic nutrients, there are also a good range of other data types. Data also come from a range of different systems (laboratory, field, batch, steady-state).

Additional contributions are welcome, and the published database will be re-published to make such additions available on open access.

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1. Introduction

Simulation models require information to support their construction and testing. That information exists in the form of both numeric and phenomenological data.

The aim of the task described here was to assemble exemplar sources of literature references to provide modellers with both the understanding of how plankton 'work' and the numeric data required for the configuration and testing of models.

The building of simulation models of plankton starts with conceptual understanding. That conceptual understanding rests at the levels of individual physiological processes through to whole ecosystems. Beyond that, numeric data are needed both to guide the initial model configuration (e.g., minimum and maximum element ratios, maximum growth rate), and also to guide optimisation ('tuning') and validation.

Accumulating useful information to help in model construction and testing presents a major challenge in plankton modelling (Flynn et al. 2022). Some models have been built around a wealth of numeric information (not all of which may be robust) but, and especially for zooplankton, most models have been built with general assumptions rather than supported with hard numeric data.

It is debatable as to whether generalisations or specifics supported by copious numeric data are more important. The reader is referred to Flynn et al. (2024a) for considerations on this matter.

1.1 Some challenges

1.1.2 Conceptual understanding

For much of biochemistry and physiology we have considerable understanding, though most comes from studies of organisms ('lab-rats') other than ecologically important plankton. Although we know of many physiological 'exceptions to the rules', to what extent those exceptions actually affect the underpinning of plankton models is another matter. For example, changes in the phospho-lipid composition of prokaryotes (Peng et al. 2019) that affect the competitive ability of some plankton in low-P waters may be described simply by extending the lower P:C quota value. On the other hand, if those same changes impact on predator-prey activity (Guillonnet et al. 2022) then an explicit description of different lipid stoichiometry may perhaps be warranted.

Some gaps in conceptual understanding have greater consequences for modelling than do others. The description of zooplankton consumer activity is an example where the extreme simplicity of the traditional approach not only conflicts with our biological understanding, but where the consequences of using alternative assumptions can totally overturn the outcome of simulations (Flynn et al. 2021).

References to publications that guide modellers on 'how the real world works' are supremely useful. That is so for all aspects of autecology and ecology, and especially so with respect to the handling of multi-stressors. Equally important, however, is clarity in terminology and the drawing of attention to features of a paper that enhance understanding of what numeric data from experiments do and do not tell us.

1.1.3 Useful vs not-so-useful numeric data

The ideal numeric data series for plankton modelling would provide a temporally well-spaced series of values for each state variable in the model, measured with good accuracy and in the appropriate units as used in the model. Further, the same types of data would be available for studies made under different conditions, and for different plankton species. Alas, the reality is very different.

In the real world, it is very rare for such a utopian data series to exist. That is so not least because in experiments the non-limiting resources are typically not measured at all, or perhaps they are determined at just at a few time points. Thus, for example, for most studies of N-limitation of phytoplankton we have no data, no idea, of how organismal P has changed. The sheer expense (pragmatically with respect to the sampling material availability, financial costs, and in terms of time) of collecting such data is often too great. Worse, to be useful the modeller really needs several data series, for setting up the model, and then for validation. Many data series are not suitable for the support of modelling, and do not necessarily report reliably what they purport set against advances in understanding.

Given suitable data series, even really complex physiological interactions can be modelled, but to undertake such studies is a major undertaking, and may be conducted specifically to help build a model. Examples include John & Flynn (2002) for dinoflagellate growth and toxicity (Figs. 1, 2), and Anning et al. (2000) used to help configure photoacclimation models (Flynn et al. 2001).

Fig. 1 The conceptual structure of the model used by John & Flynn (2002) describing the growth of the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium* under P-replete and P-deplete conditions. Parameters measured in experiments (see Fig. 2) included ammonium (A), nitrate (N), phosphate (P), cell numbers (Cell), elemental content (C, N, P, and hence N:C and P:C, the latter divided between inorganic and organic pools IPC and OPC), chlorophyll (and hence the Chl:C content), the glutamine pool (GC), and saxitoxin (TC).

Fig. 2 Data from experiments for the growth of the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium* under P-replete and P-deplete conditions (symbols), and fits of a simulation model to those data. From John & Flynn (2002).

There is also the issue of the type of experiment used to obtain data, notably steady-state vs data displaying changing dynamics over time (akin to batch-culture dynamics). Both are useful, but the dynamic series is really important because the rate at which plankton respond to changes in their environment affects their ecology. That response rate is an important trait and one that needs to be described appropriately in models else the simulation dynamics can be at strong variance with reality (e.g., for rates of photoacclimation – Flynn *et al.* 2001).

Locating even part-complete (exemplar) data series is immensely useful for modellers. However, poor data series are worse than useless to a modeller who is not an expert in the organisms they seek to simulate.

1.2 The role of transforms and surrogates

Given that invariably data series for plankton ecophysiology are incomplete, not least in that they do not report data in line with the definitions required for state variables, extracting useful information by indirect means is important.

The most widely used data transform is for biomass-C, obtained from organism size (e.g., Menden-Deuer & Lessard 2000) and numeric abundance (i.e., size \times abundance = biovolume). In mixed populations, where organisms cannot be physically separated, transforms to derive biovolumes for each species are invaluable to divide bulk measurements of elemental C between organisms. In the absence of explicit size information

a fixed size may be assumed, but this carries important caveats as under certain stressors organisms can become significantly larger or smaller (e.g., P-deplete cell size in **Fig.2**).

For zooplankton, deriving elemental biomass is problematic from many angles. The low numeric abundance levels, compounded by the destructive nature of elemental analysis, creates statistical challenges. At the upper size levels (notably large jellies) there are also logistical and pragmatic challenges of sub-sampling and preparation for the analysis. Transforms from organism size are often essential, but so too is a warning to modellers that such transforms carry caveats.

Chlorophyll is the most widely used surrogate for biomass used in marine science. It is also a parameter that needs to be considered with great care (Kruskopf & Flynn 2006) because of the variability of organismal Chl:C within and between species, and also between *in vivo* Chl and *in vitro* Chl signals. Because in many models Chl is a state variable, it is safer to use Chl data as 'Chl', and not to transform it to C or N assuming fixed Chl:C or Chl:N values.

Other transforms can be undertaken making various assumptions concerning the fate of nutrients. Thus, if nitrate is the only N-source provided to a culture, and one assumes that what inorganic N is 'missing' must be in the organisms, then one can estimate the biomass-N. Together with C estimated from biovolume, it is then possible to estimate the organism N:C. This assumes that indeed all the 'missing' nutrient is in the plankton, and that is not necessarily so. When explicit measurements of nutrient and biomass composition are taken it is common for these values to not add up and/or to stay constant over the duration of the study. The missing material may be variously within particulate and dissolved material that are not measured.

Identifying caveats in data series is important and is best done by those who well understand the plankton system in question. For field data, the situation is worse than in laboratory systems, as the plankton composition and nutrient status has an unknown nutrient-history, the abundances/concentrations are much smaller, and so statistical errors are greater.

1.3 Un-plotting and checking units

Especially in older papers, raw numeric data are rarely available in data bases or spreadsheets. The only solution then is to 'un-plot' the graphs. This assumes that the graphs themselves are correct, and their units are correct; mistakes are not uncommon and it is surprising how many graphs in published papers do not carry explicit, unambiguous, units.

Ambiguity in units include element ratios (mole or mass?) and for specific growth rates (cell-specific, C-specific, or what?). In particular, Chl-specific growth rates can be significantly at variance with C biomass-specific values, because photoacclimation can result in very rapid changes in Chl:C.

Identifying the need to un-plot or otherwise manipulate numeric data in a paper, with attention drawn to any caveats, is useful.

1.4 Controls

Controls for test scenarios are vitally important; this is especially so for predator-prey, host-virus, and indeed any study where different species of organisms are grown together. All too often the usefulness of an otherwise interesting data series is eroded by the lack of suitable control data series. For example, the elemental stoichiometry and physiological status of prey or hosts is too often not well recorded, also damaging repeatability of the study. For predator-prey systems, the consequences for the changes in prey nutrition on encountering the nutrients present with the predator upon food quality is another unknown.

The need for parallel measurements of prey-only (or for virus studies, host-only) suspensions is made more problematic if there are allelopathic or similar interactions between species. Such interactions, and how the predator affects those through selective feeding, presents at once a fascinating biological system and a real challenge for modelling. With appropriate combinations of organisms, the interactions can be teased apart (e.g., Mitra & Flynn 2006). That may be fine for laboratory systems, but for field work different problems come into play. In field studies, the most that can be done is typically to filter-fractionate and then conduct dilution experiments; there remain many unknowns in such studies (e.g., Ferreira et al. 2021), but perhaps a role for a plankton digital twin is to aid in the interpretation of those investigations. On the good side, at least with a field plankton suspension the organism interactions are real in that the organisms have evolved to grow in the same body of water; laboratory systems most often pit organisms against each other that may never encounter each other in the wild where they would have co-evolved.

In identifying papers supporting modelling, it is useful to consider whether suitable controls are present, and also draw attention to allied aspects of concern. Controls are absolutely essential for predator-prey studies, and they need to report the same breadth of data types as the test series, and ideally with the same timings.

1.5 Factoids and ‘lab-rats’

Biologists tend to emphasise differences between organisms, to explore why species *x* is more or less competitive than species *y* in a given situation. Biologists also, perhaps ironically, also like to identify exemplar, so-called ‘model’, species, in part perhaps to justify the importance of their work. This leads to the appearance of factoids in the literature, where information gained from studies on one or just a few organisms are extrapolated to general or even global terms of reference. Such activity is not helped by what could be considered as over-hyped research paper titles and abstract; many, and perhaps all, scientists are guilty of this, driven by the nature of the peer-review publishing system. However, while biologists may see through the hype in empirical reports, non-biologist modellers likely do not. By the same token, biologists are perhaps rather easily taken in by the hype of modellers, believing outputs of ‘simulations’ as facts that they would reject if only they understood what the computer code actually described.

The most well studied organisms are selected first and foremost because they grow reliably in culture, and ideally also often for microalgae that they grow in axenic culture. Research on grazers, and on other organism-organism interactions are immediately at a disadvantage in this context. There are concerns, also, that long-term maintenance of organisms in culture leads to changes in not only growth rate potential, but even in gross physiological traits, such as loss of feeding in mixoplankton (Blossom & Hansen 2021). Field work also, sampling and sub-sampling will take its toll on the more fragile organisms, and destroy delicate assemblages. Automatically, then, we select against many organisms that are important in the real world, and notably against those that have important interactions with others through allelopathic, mixoplanktonic, symbiotic, predator-prey or other means.

The classic example of a ‘lab-rat’ is of course *Escherichia coli*, used as a surrogate for all gram-negative bacteria. Plankton examples of ‘lab-rats’ include *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (an essentially Si-free diatom), *Chlamydomonas* (a freshwater chlorophyte with an unusual life cycle), and *Oxyrrhis* (a rock-pool protist zooplankton). When we study other organisms in detail, we realise that our exemplars are not really exemplars at all, although the vast bulk of the physiological machinery may be similar.

Does this mean that data obtained from the study of ‘lab-rats’ have no place in configuring or testing plankton digital twins? No, it does not mean that; they absolutely do have a place, if only for the all-important initial conceptual phase and also to test general behaviour patterns. Recall that it is more important for a simulation model to display behaviour consistent with reality than it is to describe exactly a situation of limited utility and all other situations badly. Running models with slight differences in configuration can also be used to determine whether that claimed ‘critically important difference’ in physiology really does make a difference.

Establishing whether the subject of a publication is deemed to be representative of a particular group of organisms, or otherwise, is useful.

1.6 Tuning, validating, and weighting behaviour

Numeric data are used for tuning and then validating model performance. To do this, models are first configured against (tuned to) one data series, and then their ability to describe behaviour in another condition tested against another, independent, data series. All too often, there are few if any data sets available to validate models.

One option is to replace one or other of the numeric procedures with an expert witness validation (EWV). This is best undertaken by experts in the autecology and ecology of the real organism, exploiting a model configured with a suitable interface; indeed this is a key step in making plankton digital twins. Ideally, EWV would also form part of the initial conceptual stage of model development. While historically that is likely not the case, for digital twin developments such involvement should be a given.

A common problem in models of plankton community ecology is balancing the timing vs the magnitude of bloom events, and then how to improve the simulation. During EWV, the expert will intuitively weight the relative importance of such aspects of model behaviour. Those same experts can also, however, look at data in papers and reports and provide guidance to a modeller on which data are most robust and are thus likely to be of most use for testing model behaviour.

An example is the measurement of 'uptake rates'. Because of feedbacks between nutrient transport and satiation (which occur very rapidly and potentially within the timeframe of even the first set of measurements; Flynn 1998), errors in interpretation can be made of summary experimental data for maximum rates and half saturation values (Flynn et al. 2018).

Indicating which aspects of a publication are most reliable, or conversely are perhaps best used for guidance only, is useful.

2. Method

The task, as presented to the contributors, is given in **Appendix 1**.

The database is presented as an Excel file, with sort functionality. This allows multi-level interrogation according to any/all data criteria.

The following information is provided in a 'READ ME' sheet.

THE 'Data' SHEET HAS 'FREEZE PANES' SELECTED! Alter this as you need to (access it off the 'View' menu)

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE

First check that all columns have no active filter (look on the selection arrow for the filter symbol - if it is set, then click on 'select-all').

Then for each category of interest, select to show (i.e. filter for) entries containing the required criteria. Usually that will be de-selecting 'blank'.

Repeat for each category of interest.

For example, for {copepods AND bacteria NOT phytoplankton}, select 'X' for both copepod and for bacteria, and select 'blank' for phytoplankton.

The visible records are those that satisfy your selections.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR NEW DATA ENTRY

First ensure no filters are operational, and no columns are hidden.

Navigate to the last row, marked 'insert rows above this row'; if you have more entries than there are empty rows, use the Excel 'insert rows' command.

Enter your literature data one row for each item; please insert 'X' in the columns as applicable and other information as appropriate. For help, check what others have done.

Please add an Excel 'Note' (on the 'Review' menu) to add additional information to an entry point if appropriate.

SAVE YOUR FILE AS A NEW NAME and return to KJF@PML.ac.uk

3. Results & Discussion

The current version of the database is available at the following url:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948648>

No assurance is given that any particular entry made by the indicated submitter is indeed fit for the purpose of supporting the construction of models. The supplied ORCID number for the submitter allows the interrogator to further explore the works of that submitter.

The contents of this database as of 09/04/2024 exhibited the features shown in the following plots. These features are only 1 dimensional; a full interrogation may be performed by multi-level sorting of the database.

Most entries relate to studies undertaken in laboratory, or conversely field situations (**Fig. 3**). Few report work from mesocosms. In general terms, it is very difficult to derive high quality data for configuring plankton models from field data; there are too many conflicting sources contaminating and otherwise adversely affecting the usefulness of the data source. Ultimately, however, a simulation model being used to explore real-world scenarios needs to be tested against field data. Mesocosms potentially supply a middle ground but in reality samples taken from mesocosms can be almost as problematic as one taken from the field with respect to contamination issues (e.g., separating organism types for elemental analysis). Where mesocosms are useful is in the isolation of physical events (mixing, upwelling etc.) and for facilitating the logistics of frequent replicated measurements.

Fig. 3 Arena source of the database entry. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

Most of the data come from batch-like sources; rather fewer come from steady-state studies (**Fig. 4**). In general, while steady-state (e.g., chemostat) studies are useful for obtaining values of half saturation constants, they are not useful for resolving the rate at which organisms respond to changes in their environment. Such rates of acclimation are important features in models of real-world events.

Fig. 4 Data type / source of the database entry. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, the most frequently appearing plankton type were primary producers (cyanobacteria, other phytoplankton including diatoms, and mixoplankton; **Fig. 5**). While protist grazers (mixoplankton and protist-zooplankton) were well represented, metazoan zooplankton are less well represented. Likewise, virus and bacteria/archaea are less well represented. While microbes feature well in the inevitably robust laboratory studies, the metazoan zooplankton data are more frequently from field data series, subjected to various sampling and analysis challenges.

Fig. 5 Plankton types described in the database. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

Abiotic features cover a wide range, with a broadly uniform coverage (**Fig. 6**), though dominated by temperature+light+DIN+DIP.

Fig. 6 Abiotic features described in the database. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

Of the rates, nutrient uptake was least represented (**Fig. 7**). Predation was well represented as a term although many entries were from field (and 'omic) studies, which are especially problematic for determining ingestion rates. There was some minor coverage of allelopathy and toxicity, but much more of interactions involving stoichiometric ecology.

Fig. 7 Plankton rate processes and interactions described in the database. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

Interest in stoichiometric ecology is dominated by C,N, with rather fewer entries on P biomass (**Fig. 8**). Biomass features were dominated by numeric abundance and allometry, C-biomass, and also by photopigment. A good number of entries described genomics and/or transcriptomics; none described proteomics or metabolomics. While many of the 'omics entries are tagged for biomass and rate data, it should be noted that 'omics are not well suited to providing such information (Strzepek et al. 2022). What 'omics data do reveal, however, is just how little we do know given that the experimentally derived rate data are attributed to very few species.

Fig. 8 Biomass features and 'omics described in the database. Note that entries may include data with multiple characteristics.

4. Conclusions

At the inception of this project (Flynn 2024a), it was considered essential to have access to literature considered as providing exemplar data series in support of the building of plankton models that aspire to provide digital twins. While such information undoubtedly provides a valuable resource, the numeric data may be of lesser usefulness than the elucidation of generic behavioural features of the real organisms and for providing examples of the scenarios in which a digital laboratory may be useful for the modeller. The reason for this is that, moving away from simple models that describe a form of dynamic curve-fitting exercise, we need a more comprehensive understanding of generic mechanistic functionalities. For example, while in a traditional zooplankton model, assimilation efficiency (AE) is fixed, in reality AE changes with the quantity of food available and also with the diet formulation (i.e., prey species) and the stoichiometry of components of that diet (i.e., C:N:P:lipid etc.). It is thus more important to understand how AE varies with diet and other factors such as pH (Cripps et al. 2016) than it is to amass data in an attempt to derive an average fixed AE value.

An important challenge is the development of new field techniques for the robust determination of biomass and metabolic/ecological activities for all plankton types for deployment from autonomous platforms. Within that, the smaller plankton types (<10 μ m), and more delicate forms, require most attention. To what extent information from 'omics contribute to modelling, through provision of species-specific biomass and rate

process data, is another important topic that warrants urgent attention (Strzepek et al. 2022). That 'omics data are semi-quantitative needs to be set against how problematic are the alternative flow cytometric and optical approaches for determining numeric abundance and biomass for different species. Allocating those species into useful plankton functional groups for modelling is another challenge again. Because functional grouping (Weithoff 2003) depends on both bottom-up and top-down interactions, that challenge will require the engagement of ecologists to resolve.

From other parts of the project (Flynn et al. 2024a, b, c), a clearer vision has emerged as to what the end user, as plankton researchers, desire from models and also how progress can be best made. The database developed in this project will hopefully promote others to contribute entries, and also to consider how they may better present their work in support of modelling.

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Appendix 1

The following is the text of the task as provided to the contributors. A template Excel, with an example, was supplied. Returns were collated into a single Excel.

The Task

A.1 Selecting references

You are asked to recommend any publications that you feel would provide useful guidance or useful numeric data to support the construction of plankton models.

Your own publications likely provide a useful resource, and a resource for which the caveats (often not emphasised in the text of a paper and/or which may have developed in the years since publication) will be well understood.

Please only propose references for papers that you have high confidence in, not just in the headline, but critically in the data present either in the main text or in the supplementary material. Often, useful data series are buried in papers (perhaps in the appendix) reporting one facet of plankton ecophysiology.

Papers of summary data (e.g. transport kinetics, maximum growth rates) can be useful, but please raise any concerns about the data entries. Such reviews may include data values that, on inspection of the source papers, are not as they claim (e.g., half saturation constant for growth, not for transport) or are otherwise ambiguous. **Please propose such references with care.**

Papers reporting well-founded transforms and other relationships (e.g., activation energy or Q_{10} vs temperature), are welcome.

Papers that are critical of widely used methods, or of theories or concepts, are especially welcome.

A.2 Open access

If there are open access variants of the paper, please point to the location of such material.

A.3 Formatting the publication entry

Please enter the publication details, and additional commentary options, into the accompanying Excel spreadsheet. An example is given for you.

Comments on certain aspects of the submission are entered in the appropriate cells, but there are also free-text entry points as well. Entry options include the 'arena' of the science; there is an option here for reviews and papers reporting transforms etc.

Please provide sufficient information on the publication itself to enable its location. If you wish to format the reference, please use the 'APA' format. The easiest way to achieve this is to use Google Scholar to find the work, select 'cite' and copy/paste the 'APA' format into the Excel cell.

You can enter as many publications as you wish.

'Frequently Asked Questions' (FAQs)

Can I list my own papers?

A: Yes, of course. You are best placed to judge how useful and reliable your own works are in the support of this task.

Does it matter how old is the publication?

A. No. All that matters is the quality of the data collected, and its suitability for support of modelling (i.e., good temporal series, unambiguous units etc.).

Are papers reporting results based on organism abundance, or Chl, without any reliable means to determine real (elemental) biomass, really of no use for this Task?

A. Sadly, that is essentially correct. If there is no way to ascertain the actual amount of organism biomass in a reliable robust fashion then the data are of limited use for modelling. The exception may be in short-term incubations where the biomass can at least be assumed to be invariant in its relationship with numeric abundance.

Do I have to exhaustively fill out the columns in the spreadsheet?

A. No, provided that the entry is otherwise clear in its contribution to the Task (but the more the better!).